

TOP 1 CITED PAPERS

**Computer Science & Engineering: An
International Journal (CSEIJ)**

ISSN : 2231 - 329X (Online) ; 2231 - 3583 (Print)

<https://www.cseij.org/index.html>

IMAGE SEGMENTATION BY USING THRESHOLDING TECHNIQUES FOR MEDICAL IMAGES

Senthilkumaran N¹ and Vaithegi S²

¹Department of Computer Science and Application, Gandhigram Rural Institute,
Dindigul

²Deemed University, Gandhigram, Dindigul

ABSTRACT

Image binarization is the process of separation of pixel values into two groups, black as background and white as foreground. Thresholding can be categorized into global thresholding and local thresholding. This paper describes a locally adaptive thresholding technique that removes background by using local mean and standard deviation. Most common and simplest approach to segment an image is using thresholding. In this work we present an efficient implementation for thresholding and give a detailed comparison of Niblack and sauvola local thresholding algorithm. Niblack and sauvola thresholding algorithm is implemented on medical images. The quality of segmented image is measured by statistical parameters: Jaccard Similarity Coefficient, Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR).

KEYWORDS

Thresholding, Niblack, Sauvola, PSNR, Jaccard

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/cseij/V6N1/6116cseij01.pdf>

Volume Link: <https://www.cseij.org/vol6.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Hui Zhang, Jason E.Fritts, Sally A. Goldman,” [Image Segmentation Evaluation: A Survey Unsupervised Methods](#)”,2008.
- [2] Nir Milstein, “[Image Segmentation by Adaptive Thresholding](#)”,Spring 1998.
- [3] Sang uk lee, seok yoon chung and Rae hong park, “[A Comparative Performance Study of Several Global Thresholding Techniques for Segmentation](#)”, Computer Vision Graphics And Image Processing52, 171-190, 1990
- [4] Graham Leedham, Chen Yan, Kalyan Takru, Joie Hadi Nata Tan and Li Mian, “Comparison of Some Thresholding Algorithms for Text/Background Segmentation in Difficult Document Images”,Proceedings of the Seventh International Conference on Document Analysis and Recognition , 2003.
- [5] Graham Leedham, Chen Yan, Kalyan Takru, Joie Hadi Nata Tan and Li Mian,” Comparison of Some Thresholding Algorithms forText/Background Segmentation in Difficult Document Images”,2003.
- [6] O. Imocha Singh, Tejmani Sinam “[Local Contrast and Mean based Thresholding Technique in Image Binarization](#)” International Journal of Computer Applications (0975 – 8887) Volume 51–No.6, August 2012.
- [7] Er.Nirpjeet kaur, Er Rajpreet kaur “[A review on various methods of image thresholding](#)” (IJCSE).
- [8] Bülent Sankura, Mehmet Sezginb “[Survey over image thresholding techniques and quantitative performance evaluation](#)” Journal of Electronic Imaging 13(1), 146–165 (January 2009).
- [9] 1.Priyanka G. Kumbhar, 2 Prof. Sushilkumar N. Holambe,” A Review of Image Thresholding Techniques”, International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering , Volume 5, Issue 6, June 2015.
- [10] T.Romen Singh¹, Sudipta Roy², O.Imocha Singh³, Tejmani Sinam⁴, Kh.Manglem Singh, “[A New Local Adaptive Thresholding Technique in Binarization](#),” IJCSI International Journal of Computer Science Issues, Vol. 8, Issue 6, No 2, November 2011.
- [11] Rukhsar Firdousi, Shaheen Parveen,” Local Thresholding Techniques in Image Binarization”, International Journal Of Engineering And Computer Science ISSN:2319-7242 Volume 3 Issue 3 March, 2014 Page No. 4062-4065.

- [12] T.Romen Singh, Sudipta Roy, O.Imocha Singh, Tejmani Sinam, Kh.Manglem Singh
“A New Local Adaptive Thresholding Technique in Binarization” IJCSI
International Journal of Computer Science Issues, Vol. 8, Issue 6, No 2, November
2011.
- [13] Er.Nirpjeet kaur, Er Rajpreet kaur “[A review on various methods of image thresholding](#)” (IJCSE).
- [14] Graham Leedham, Chen Yan, Kalyan Takru, Joie Hadi Nata Tan and Li Mian
“Thresholding Algorithms for Text/Background Segmentation in Difficult
Document Images” Seventh International Conference on Document Analysis and
Recognition (ICDAR 2010).
- [15] Niblack (1986), [An Introduction to Digital Image Processing](#), pp. 115 - 116,
Prentice Hall.
- [16] J. Sauvola and M. Pietikainen, “[Adaptive document image binarization](#),” Pattern
Recognition 33(2), pp. 225–236, 2000.

AUTHORS

S.vaithegi doing M.phil computer science in Gandhigram Rural Institute-
Deemed University, TamilNadu and done in Master of computer Application
in kumarasamy Engineering College TamilNadu. Her research area include
image processing.

